

Assessment of Routine Viral Load Monitoring Services and Performance of HIV Projects. A Case of Health Facilities in Nairobi County, Kenya

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Abstract:

Antiretroviral therapy (ART) is a cornerstone of HIV management, and viral load testing serves as the gold standard for assessing drug effectiveness and confirming treatment adherence. The objectives set by The Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS) for HIV care and treatment still encounter challenges, particularly in achieving improved access to ART and associated services, including essential laboratory viral load monitoring. This study investigated gaps in routine viral load monitoring within the 95-95-95 cascade, with particular emphasis on the final 95%, which remains unattained across individual, programmatic, and population

levels. The research adopted a cross-sectional survey design with a pragmatic approach, focusing on healthcare professionals providing HIV services in clinics in Nairobi. A proportional sample of 226 respondents was collected from a population of 550 to gather qualitative and quantitative data. The study yielded a 90% response rate, with 96% agreement among respondents. The findings revealed a moderately low but statistically significant positive correlation ($r=0.479<0.05$). The R^2 value of 0.230 explained 23.3% of project performance and displayed statistical significance ($p\text{-value}=0.000<0.05$). Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating a substantial relationship between routine viral load monitoring services and the performance of HIV projects. In light of these results, the study recommends the implementation of a combination of feasible strategies, tailored to differentiated care models, to address challenges in low-resource settings across various population groups. These strategies aim to enhance adherence and improve viral load suppression rates, thus promoting the objectives of HIV care and treatment.

Keywords: Routine Viral load monitoring, HIV projects, antiretroviral therapy, healthcare workers, Nairobi County.

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Introduction

The UNAIDS targets referred to as the 95-95-95 cascade include assisted partner notification services, test-and-treat, and routine viral load monitoring services respectively (Joint United Nations Programme on HIV and AIDS, 2019). By the end of 2018, the WHO convened a post-implementation conference with experts to review the future of the guidelines for service delivery and provided updated guidelines in early 2021. ARVs were proportionately high as well as retention and a systematic review of 50 studies found that adherence measures could not identify PLHIV with poor adherence resulting in unsuppressed viral loads (Ford et al., 2018).

Literature Review

HIV projects entail the achievement of the UNAIDS' 95-95-95 targets along the continuum of care: identifying 95% of people living with HIV who do not know their status, initiating 95% of those diagnosed with HIV, and ensuring 95% of those started on ART remain on treatment and achieve viral load suppression. These three targets were studied through partner notification services (PNS), test-and-treat, and routine viral load monitoring services respectively. The literature was reviewed in terms of projects that utilize these strategies that reduce burdens in the health care system leading to improved patient outcomes on treatment and reaching epidemic control. The performance of HIV projects requires robust data capture and reporting systems monitoring the advancement of the set goals (Sacks-Davis et al., 2018) The performance of HIV projects entails routine VL testing for clients on ART leading to sustained viral suppression.

To address challenges in the implementation of the third 95, a 6-year longitudinal review was done to evaluate the progress toward public health interventions using results at baseline testing, the proportion of those eligible, and those that received the service. The findings showed low coverage levels and follow-up for those on ART, which occasioned poor regimen

switches among the study population leading to poor suppression levels (Pham et al., 2022).

In some parts of Asia, viral load testing for clients on ART has been reported as a challenge while assessing the efficacy of response to therapy. A longitudinal study was conducted to test treatment failure and the related factors to regimen switches. A comparison between routine and non-routine testing sites showed that viral failure rate was higher in the latter, while age was also noted as a contributing factor in patients below 50 years of age, and being at a routine testing site had a higher chance of drug-switching to a second line. The main observation was that a lack of routine viral testing was associated with viral failure (Teeraananchai et al., 2022).

Since the WHO guidelines regarding VL testing among PLHIV were launched in the year 2016, indications of sustained suppression for patients at risk of not attaining suppression after being enrolled in enhanced adherence support sessions have been noticeably low. As a result, a one-time study was conducted in Zimbabwe using laboratory testing data from both routine and post-EAC VL monitoring. The findings showed that out of the seven tests done only one had not suppressed after the EACs, among the groups, adolescents on ART were at a higher risk of not suppressing, while those receiving VL tests after the 2016 guidelines were at a higher chance of attaining viral suppression. As a result, the country showed a remarkable chance of reaching the third 95 of the UNAIDS goal on epidemic control (Mhlanga et al., 2022)

A controlled clinical trial was conducted in Kenya among children below 14 years of age living with HIV to establish an accessible and gainful approach to improving VL uptake and suppression rates through point-of-care testing approaches. The results indicated that a year after enrollment, the suppression rates did not differ between the intervention and control groups at 90% and 92% respectively. This study implied that there was a reduced response time when using the point-of-care testing strategies and to reduce the cases of viremia among this

group of patients, psychosocial support should be considered (Patel et al., 2022)

In South Africa's Khayelitsha township, a study was carried out to evaluate the rationality of regularly conveyed VL suppression of 89% to address the challenges from the documented routine data. The retrospective cohort study in 2016 sampled 1,035 client file suppression rates that were measured by comparing the testing site and electronic data. Logistic regression was used to classify the features related to laboratory data and stated VL testing. The findings indicated that 84% of routine tests were done, and suppression was estimated at 82% for children below 15 years and pregnant than in men and the general population, and work was required to cover the 16% of records missed by regular testing (Euvrard et al., 2019a).

Theoretical Framework

Research using the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) has explained and predicted a variety of human behaviors since 1967. Based on the premise that humans are rational and that the behaviors being explored are under volitional control, the theory provides a construct that links individual beliefs, attitudes, intentions, and behavior (Fishbein et al., 1994).

The TRA provides a context for linking the behavioral or cognitive structures and the

normative beliefs that impact individual attitudes and norms that inform the intent to accomplish a behavior. In this case, an individual's risk perception is key in engaging in HIV prevention behavior like medical male circumcision, correct and consistent condom use, and adherence to PrEP. The expectation that one is to remain HIV-free, and if infected remain virally suppressed are key determinants of behavior change and confining to social norms and expectations. Hence, this theory states that a person's intention remains the best indicator that the desired behavior will occur, leading to reduced infection rates, morbidity, and mortality due to the disease.

This model largely supports a linear process in which changes in an individual's behavioral and normative beliefs will ultimately affect the individual's actual behavior, and this can be applied in the HIV continuum of care where there is interdependence between each intervention and the next one (from testing HIV-positive to starting ART to remaining virally suppressed). However, this has its personal and implementation challenges where clients do not know their status, fall out of treatment, and due to poor adherence to treatment do not achieve viral suppression due to individual or programmatic gaps (Waldby et al., 1993).

Figure 1. Theory of Reasoned Action

Source: Otieno et al., 2015

Materials and Methods

This study adopted the pragmatism research paradigm, as it allowed the researcher to apply various methods in responding to the research questions based on their application. Further, it adopted a retrospective cross-sectional descriptive survey design which enhances the simultaneous aggregation of both qualitative and quantitative forms of data (Wambugu et al., 2015).

The study targeted 550 healthcare workers distributed across the 41 health facilities in the 10 sub-counties in Nairobi County. Based on the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table of sample size determination, a sample size of 226 was desired from a population of 550 from the study area. Since the study population was stratified, the proportionate random sampling technique was used where each stratum was divided by the total population and multiplied by the obtained sample size as it has more statistical precision than simple random sampling (Wambugu et al., 2015).

This formula was used to determine the number of respondents per strata: $ns = p \cdot P / S$; where ns was the desired strata sample size, p is the strata population, P is the total population and S is the sample total size.

Quantitative data was obtained through a virtual questionnaire from these six cadres: clinical officers, nurses, HIV testing services counselors, health records and information officers, and laboratory and pharmacy technologists as direct service delivery staff. Simple random sampling generated using a Microsoft Excel table of random numbers was used to get the number of the participating clinics and the respective cadres of staff from each site, and a sampling frame was drawn from the sites since they all contain similar information using a 5-point Likert Scale (5. Strongly agree, 4. Agree, 3. Neutral, 2. Disagree, and 1. Strongly disagree).

Qualitative data was obtained through a purposive sampling of 6 key informant interviews with the sub-county and project team as supervisors and coordinators of HIV services.

Similarly, Focus Group Discussions were conducted with peer educators and mentor-mothers as PLHIVs. A total of 5 FGDs consisting of up to 12 participants was considered suitable to gather detailed information. This was also used for triangulation with the questionnaire data.

Pilot testing was done using 10% of the sample to identify relevant study factors and evaluate the acceptability of the tools among participants (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003). Validity was enhanced through input from experts in HIV programming. Further triangulation used facilitators across sites and locations. Consistency in results provided additional evidence of validity, thereby enhancing the credibility of the study. Cronbach's Alpha (1951) reliability coefficient of 0.7 was used to ensure internal consistency.

Research permits and approvals were obtained from the National Commission for Science, Technology, and Innovation (NACOSTI), Kenyatta National Hospital (KNH)/University of Nairobi Ethical and Scientific Review Committee (KNH-UoN ERC), and the Nairobi County Health Management Team.

Results

The Shapiro-Wilk test (SW-test) was used to test the normality of the data, a fundamental assumption for testing suitability for parametric analysis. Correlation analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation was done to establish the relationship/ strength and direction between the predictor and the response variable. The values ranged between +1 and -1 indicating a perfect positive correlation and a perfect negative correlation.

Background Information

This was obtained through the highest education level and years of experience in Table 1.

Table 1. Highest Level of Education

Category	Frequencies	Percentage
Certificate	13	6.4
Diploma	133	65.5
Graduate	48	23.6
Postgraduate	9	4.4
Total	203	100

Source: Nairobi County Health Department; Integrated Human Resource Information System (HRIS), (2020).

The findings showed that the majority of the participants 133(65.5%) were diplomas holders, 48(23.6%) degree level, 13(6.4%) were certificate, and lastly, only 9(4.4%) were postgraduates. This implies that a majority of 190(93.6%) of the healthcare workers' level of education was high and therefore known to have the capacity to understand and articulate matters regarding health education. They are also likely to keep up with the fast-changing guidelines in HIV management on drug regimens for patient types for age, gender, population type, food-and-drug interactions, and those with underlying clinical conditions.

Table 2. Years of experience in HIV Projects

Category	Frequencies	Percentage
Below 5 years	186	91.6
6 – 10 years	13	6.4
11 – 15 years	4	2.0
Total	203	100

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics on Performance of HIV Projects

Likert Scale	Interval Scale/Score	Frequencies	Percentage
Strongly Disagree	12-21	0	0.0
Disagree	22-31	0	0.0
Neutral	32-41	18	8.9
Agree	42-51	143	70.4
Strongly Agree	52-61	42	20.7
	Total	203	100

Source: Nairobi County Health Department; Integrated Human Resource Information System (HRIS), (2020).

The results indicated that the majority of the respondents agreed that viral load suppression

Source: Nairobi County Health Department; Integrated Human Resource Information System (HRIS), (2020).

The study also sought from the respondents the number of years of experience in HIV/AIDS projects which can be related to the quality of service in terms of continuous improvement in the performance of the projects. Table 4.2 shows that 186(91.6%) of the respondents had worked for less than 5 years, 13(6.4%) between 6-10 years, and 4(2.0%) 11-15 years respectively. This implied that the majority of the healthcare workers had a wealth of knowledge and experience suitable for the provision of detailed information on matters related to the provision of the most recent guidelines in quality patient care that promote the uptake of both preventive and curative health-seeking behavior.

Performance of HIV Projects

The study found it necessary to collect both quantitative and qualitative data on the response variable. The variable indicators were the number of HIV-positive clients with the documented result and the percentage of viral load suppression. The respondents were asked to give their opinion on the performance of HIV projects in health facilities. A 5-point Likert scale of range 1 to 5 was used where 1= Strongly Disagree (SD), 2= Disagree (D), 3= Neutral (N), 4= Agree (A), and 5=Strongly Agree (SA). The results are presented in Table 3.

rates are higher among those newly initiated on ART and that retention rates are higher during

the test-and-treat compared to the previous era. 143(70.4%) agreed with the statements, 42(20.7) agreed, 18 (8.9%) respondents had a neutral view, and none 0 (0%) of the respondents neither strongly disagreed nor disagreed with the statements put across regarding the performance of HIV projects. This is supported by previous studies that show that clients must undergo the whole spectrum of care from identification to achieving and maintaining viral suppression, where high VL coverage levels and follow-up

facilitate regimen switches leading to high suppression levels (Pham et al., 2022)

Descriptive Statistics on Routine Viral Load Monitoring Services

The following indicators that guided the development of the statements; routine viral load testing; documentation of results; service coverage; turnaround time and sample networking.

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics on Routine Viral Load Monitoring Services

Likert Scale	Interval Scale/Score	Frequencies	Percentage
Strongly Disagree	12-21	0	0.0
Disagree	22-31	0	0.0
Neutral	32-41	8	3.9
Agree	42-51	104	51.2
Strongly Agree	52-61	91	44.8
	Total	203	100

Source: Nairobi County Health Department; Integrated Human Resource Information System (HRIS), (2020).

The output showed that the majority 140(51.2%) agreed with the statements regarding routine viral load testing, 91(44.8) strongly agreed, 8 (3.9%) respondents had a neutral view, while lastly none 0 (0%) of the respondents neither strongly disagreed nor disagreed with the statements put across regarding HIV projects. These findings suggest a positive perception and acceptance of routine viral load monitoring services among the respondents. Most of the participants agreed or strongly agreed with the

importance and effectiveness of routine viral load testing in promotion. This is in line with studies on the role of viral suppression rates among adults in Uganda for newly initiated versus clients previously on ART, which emphasize the importance of monitoring suppression rates for new clients in line with the WHO regulations (Joint United Nations Programme on HIV and AIDS (UNAIDS), 2019).

Table 5. Statistics on Routine Viral Load Monitoring Services and Performance of HIV Projects

N Statistic	Range Statistic	Minimum Statistic	Maximum Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Std. Deviation
203	22	38	60	50.42	0.360	5.131

Source: Nairobi County Health Department; Integrated Human Resource Information System (HRIS), (2020).

Results from Table 5 indicate that there was no missing data. The range statistic (22) was the difference between the maximum (60) and minimum (38) perception scores on viral load

monitoring services. The mean statistic (50.42) was the mean perception of the respondents, and lay in the fourth category (42-51), meaning that most of the respondents agreed with the

statements put across regarding routine viral load monitoring services, the mean standard error (0.360) was very low, meaning that the mean of the sample was very close to the population mean, the standard deviation statistic (5.131) was very small meaning all the scores were clustering around the mean. This is supported by other research supporting routine

VL monitoring and that being at a routine testing site has a higher chance of drug-switching which significantly reduces the factors associated with viral failure (Teeraananchai et al., 2022).

Correlational Analysis of Routine Viral Load Monitoring and Performance of HIV Projects

Table 6. Correlational Analysis

Variable		Viral Load	Performance
Viral Load	Pearson Correlation	1	0.479**
	Sig. (2-Tailed)		0.000
	n	203	203
Performance	Pearson Correlation	0.479**	1
	Sig. (2-Tailed)	0.000	
	n	203	203

Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Source: Nairobi County Health Department; Integrated Human Resource Information System (HRIS), (2020).

This showed a moderate positive correlation (0.479), with a significance value of 0.000, implying that as the service update increases, so are the chances of improving performance of

HIV projects in Nairobi County. These highlight the importance of implementing effective practices to improve health outcomes for individuals being served in the projects.

Table 7. One-Way ANOVA Comparison of Means

Category	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Neutral	8	41.50	2.9277	1.0351	39.0524	43.948
Agree	104	47.15	2.77915	0.2725	46.6134	47.694
Strongly Agree	91	49.55	6.15045	0.6447	48.2686	50.83
	203	48.006	4.92066	0.34536	47.3239	48.6859

Source: Nairobi County Health Department; Integrated Human Resource Information System (HRIS), (2020).

The findings indicate that comparison in the means between the three categories; those who strongly agreed had the highest mean score (49.55), followed by agreed (47.15), and neutral (41.50). The value ($p=0.000 \leq 0.05$), indicated that there was evidence to reject the null hypothesis of significant differences in performance. Therefore, the findings suggest

that performance of routine viral load monitoring services did not significantly vary among respondents who had a neutral opinion, agreed, or strongly agreed on the importance of these services. Overall, the results imply that while there were slight differences in mean scores, there was no statistically significant difference.

Table 8. ANOVA Between Groups ANOVA^a

Factor	Sum of Squares	d.f	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	630.929	2	315.465	14.810	0.000
Within Groups	4260.066	200	21.300		
Total	4890.995	202			

Source: Nairobi County Health Department; Integrated Human Resource Information System (HRIS), (2020).

To establish the relationship between the independent and dependent variables, an analysis of variance was applied as presented in Table 8. It was established that the F-significance value of 0.000 was less than 0.05 (p-value=0.000 < 0.05). The F-calculated (14.810) was significantly larger than the critical value of F (3.89). Therefore, reject the null hypothesis that there was a significant relationship between routine viral load monitoring services and performance of HIV projects in health facilities. These research findings, therefore, show that management of HIV clients via routine viral load testing to achieve and sustain high suppression rates improves health and reduces deaths related to the infection. Many countries have continually invested in increasing viral load services to meet the third 95% of sustained suppressed viral loads by 2030 (Consolidated strategic information guidelines for HIV in the health sector, 2015).

Regression Analysis

A simple linear regression model was applied to fulfill the requirements of the objective.

H₀: There was no significant relationship between VL Monitoring and Performance of HIV Projects using the model:

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + e \tag{1}$$

Where:

y= Performance of HIV Projects;

β₀=Constant,

β₁= beta coefficient,

X₁= Routine Viral Load Monitoring,

e= error term

Table 9. Regression Analysis: Model Summary

(a) Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.479 ^a	0.230	0.226	4.32923

Source: Nairobi County Health Department; Integrated Human Resource Information System (HRIS), (2020).

The R-value (0.479) showed a moderate positive correlation. The R Square (0.230) meant it explained that 23.0% performance of HIV

projects, while the remaining 77.0% was explained by other factors not accounted for in the model.

Table 10. Regression Analysis: Goodness-of-Fit ANOVA

(b) Goodness-of-Fit ANOVA						
Model	Factor	Sum of Squares	d.f	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1123.814	1	1123.814	59.9621	0.000 ^b
	Residual	3767.181	201	18.742		

	Total	4890.995	202		
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Source: Nairobi County Health Department; Integrated Human Resource Information System (HRIS), (2020).

The calculated F-value (59.962) was higher than the critical F-value (3.89), meaning that the regression model explained the statistically

significant relationship between the two variables and the goodness of fit of the model at p-value = 0.000.

Table 11. Regression Analysis: Beta Coefficients

(c) Beta Coefficients					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
1	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	24.824	3.009		8.250	0.000
Routine VL	0.460	0.059	0.479	7.743	0.000
a. Dependent Variable: Performance of HIV Projects					
b. Predictors: (Constant) Routine Viral Load					

Source: Nairobi County Health Department; Integrated Human Resource Information System (HRIS), (2020).

The R-value (0.479) showed a moderate positive correlation. Performance of HIV Projects = 24.824 + 0.479 (Routine Viral Load Testing Services) + e.

The overall model summary (R=0.479, R²=0.230, adjusted R²=0.226, F(1,202) = 59.962, p=0.000≤0.05) was explained by the constant coefficient (24.824) representing the expected value of HIV project performance when all predictor variables were set to zero. The beta coefficient (0.479) signified the change in one unit in viral load services, increased project performance by 47.9%. The t-value (7.743) suggested that the coefficient for the services holds statistical significance (p-value=0.000≤0.05), therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected meaning that routine viral load monitoring services had a significant relationship with performance of HIV projects in Nairobi County.

The findings of this study indicate that the uptake of routine viral load monitoring plays a crucial role in improving health outcomes and reducing deaths related to HIV infection. Many countries have recognized the importance of increasing viral load services to achieve the goal of sustained suppression rates as reinforced in

this study in line with the year 2030 goals (Consolidated strategic information guidelines for HIV in the health sector, 2015).

Further descriptive analysis from the current study found that documentation of routine testing is crucial in monitoring VL coverage; structures and skilled workforce are determinants of service uptake; digital applications can overcome limitations of timely access to test results; low levels of awareness of the importance of VL testing; test results and their implications can hinder coverage; offering enhanced adherence and psychosocial support addresses challenges of unsuppressed VL; mechanisms to track viral load results turn-around times influence VL testing uptake and facilities with dedicated lab staff that receive supportive supervision in the delivery of viral load services contribute to routine viral load monitoring influencing performance of HIV projects among Healthcare workers in health facilities.

The study further gathered information on qualitative information regarding routine viral load monitoring and performance of HIV projects in health facilities. Responses obtained from the interviews with the stakeholders about

routine viral load monitoring were captured. The respondents were required to provide information on the challenges involved in routine viral load monitoring concerning access to viral load testing labs, staff, mechanisms to reduce the number of rejected viral load samples, and measures to improve viral load turn-around times. Several respondents had the following to share.

“There is a standard mechanism for ensuring that all clients access viral load testing. There are sample referral networks where motorbikes collect samples from health facilities depending on the level of the facility. In high-volume facilities, riders collect samples even twice a day”.

“Facilities lacking partner support may have challenges accessing Viral Load. Private facilities and consultancy centres experience shortages because the commodities and procedures are expensive as clients have to pay or use insurance which sometimes does not cover certain procedures”.

“Facilities in HIV donor programs are better. Riders check that sample acceptance and sample rejection criteria are met. Concerning turnaround time, it takes to collect, receive, analyse, test, and collect results for dispatch. NASCOP Viral Load portal monitors all the information. The turnaround time could be an issue of workload. This could be addressed by devolving testing by empowering some counties with labs whilst ensuring quality. During quarterly meetings for stakeholders or Technical Working Groups (TWG) should address any challenges concerning VL”.

Discussion

Descriptive data showed that the majority 140(51.2%) agreed with the statements regarding routine viral load testing, 91(44.8) strongly agreed, 8 (3.9%) respondents had a neutral view, while none 0 (0%) of the respondents neither strongly disagreed nor disagreed with the statements. The mean statistic (50.42) was the mean perception of the respondents and lay in the fourth category (42-51), meaning that most of the majority of the respondents agreed with

the statements, while the mean standard error (0.360) was very low, meaning that the mean of the sample was very close to the population mean. The standard deviation (5.131) was very small meaning all the scores were clustering around the mean indicating a high level of agreement among the respondents. Post hoc results showed there were no significant differences between respondents in the neutral ($p=0.003<0.05$) and agreed ($p=0.000<0.05$) categories, meaning convergence in the perceptions about the importance of viral load testing in guaranteeing high suppression rates.

Correlation analysis results showed a moderate positive correlation (0.479), concluding an increase in VL services increased project performance ($r=0.479$, $p<0.05$). Analysis of variance observed there were no significant differences in the perceptions of respondents who had a neutral opinion, agreed, or strongly agreed regarding the importance of the service ($p=0.000<0.05$). The F-calculated (59.962) was significantly larger than the critical value of F (3.89), indicating that the model had sufficient explanatory power and achieved a good fit for statistical significance. The overall model summary ($R=0.479$, $R^2=0.230$, adjusted $R^2=0.226$, $F(1,202) = 59.962$, $p=0.000\leq 0.05$). The R^2 (0.226) indicated that 22.6% of the variation in performance can be explained by routine viral load testing with all other factors held constant. The rejection of the null hypothesis proposed a significant relationship between the VL testing performance of HIV projects.

Qualitative data results showed that there were mechanisms to ensure access to viral load testing services through sample referral networks, increasing access to the service as well as reducing the turn-around time for improved clinical care and patient outcomes.

Conclusion

A notable number of participants indicated strong agreement with the statements concerning the impact of routine viral load services. The mean perception of respondents

firmly aligned within the strongly agreeing category, underscoring the consensus on the significant role in documentation and their subsequent application. The minimal mean standard error emphasizes the close distribution of the sample mean around the population mean, affirming the representativeness of the sample. This configuration emphasizes the population's view that swift turn-around times for result delivery are of paramount importance. The small deviation statistic signifies the convergence of scores around the mean, indicating a robust agreement among participants regarding the significance of viral load suppression in patient care. An observed moderate positive correlation between the variables emerged, and no remarkable dissimilarities emerged among the categories of neutral, agreement, or strong agreement. Consequently, the null hypothesis proposing a substantial relationship between routine viral load monitoring services and HIV project performance was rejected. This outcome emphasizes the critical role of result accessibility and documentation in fostering increased service utilization. This, in turn, contributes to the attainment and sustenance of viral load suppression, which significantly impacts the healthcare workforce in Nairobi County.

Recommendations

The high levels of agreement amongst the respondents on the value of viral load suppression in patient care reiterates the integration of psychosocial support to enhance sustained viral suppression rates. The study recommends ARV optimization of children to efavirenz-based regimens as they were reported to be 2 times more likely to attain viral load suppression rates. It also recommends sites having sample networking facilities to facilitate short turn-around times in receiving VL results for quality of care. Longitudinal studies to assess the long-term impact and sustainability of HIV projects on healthcare workers' performance and patient outcomes. This can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness and durability of

interventions over time and identify any potential challenges or areas for improvement.

Suggestions for Further Studies

The study had these suggestions for further research: The current study focused on service uptake among healthcare workers. Other studies may consider investigating why antiretroviral (ART) retention rates are higher in private than public hospitals. This is because this study was limited to healthcare workers' uptake of HIV service delivery.

Contributions to the Body of knowledge

Documentation of routine testing was crucial in monitoring viral load coverage. Further, structures to support sample networking and a dedicated skilled workforce that receives supportive supervision were determinants of service uptake, and utilization of digital applications to address timely access to results. Mechanisms to track viral load results turn-around times were seen to influence service uptake and led to better client outcomes by having a standard operating mechanism for ensuring that all clients access viral load testing. Offering enhanced adherence and psychosocial support was reported to improve suppression rates.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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